

Vulnerability of Internally Displaced Persons and Meta governance

Ningombam Sympathy Devi¹ & Dr. Mangoljao Maibam²

Abstract:

The ongoing Manipur crisis has many consequences for the state's political, social, and economic conditions. Most importantly, the people internally displaced because of such a crisis are the worst. Their current means of survival are at risk. No proper house or shelter, the basic need, is being threatened. Lack of Necessary attention or regular checks of the Government from the Government, NGOs, clubs, or any organization can be witnessed compared to a few months after May 3, 2023. Their children's education and necessities besides shelter, such as food and clothing, have become challenging. Most of them are unemployed and unskilled and lack resources to support their survival; their right to life is being threatened. The paper aims to find a likely solution to this vulnerability through meta-governance. The paper also includes the analysis of Government relations with the community in handling such vulnerability during a crisis. So, what initiatives does the Government take to fulfill these citizens' rights, and how can meta-governance become a likely solution for their vulnerability?

Keywords: Crisis, Displacement, Government, Meta governance, Rights.

Introduction

As we have witnessed, severe human lives were lost, houses were burnt down, and many more after crimes and unwanted happenings followed the ethnic clashes that started in Manipur on May 3, 2024. However, can we consider it an ethnic clash, or is it something else that has not been clear to date as the causes of the conflict are varied, and various reasons may be responsible politically, socially, or economically? Besides the cause of the conflict and its solution and all the protests and actions, the only fact that cannot be neglected is the vulnerability of the people in the state. Specially internally displaced persons are the

¹ Research Scholar, Department of Political Science, Manipur University, Canchipur

² Assistant Professor, Department of Political Science, Manipur University, Canchipur

immediate victims of such conflict. Internally displaced people include those who have fled their homes but remain within the national borders. Many such victims have become internally displaced persons due to such conflict and chaos. Overnight, they have become homeless, lost loved ones, lost their means of livelihood, and underwent many traumatic events that may have a solid psychological impact for the rest of their lives. They have been affected more severely than anybody else because of the conflict.

Methodology

The study includes qualitative analysis, descriptive analysis of articles, newspapers, News updates during the crisis, personal interactions of IDPs in several relief camps, and IDPs selling goods on the roadside. The data collected are from primary and secondary sources, which include newspapers, both local and national; articles or journals, both national and international; news channels, discussions, and interviews, which are available online; public meetings, slogans, rallies, personal communications of victims individually, in clusters.

Limitations Of the Study

It focuses on the ongoing crisis in Manipur, which has come in huge flames since May 3, 2023. Personal interactions include victims of the Meitei community at different relief camps. In contrast, the viewpoints of other communities and Kuki communities are based on video records from a few news channels, their CSOs, and other organizational notices. Another limitation of the study is that it is only confined to qualitative analysis.

Conditions And Vulnerability of the IDPS

The voices of victims, internally displaced persons, as recorded by different local, national, and international media, have proven that they are insecure about their lives; they feel threatened going back to their homes even if they strongly desire it and call for immediate and seek help from governments state as well central to find a possible solution. IDPs can also be classified based on the crisis- the first one includes those who lost their homes permanently, and the other one is those who fled away due to fear of attack. These two IDPs also have different concerns, and the traumatic responses are varied. In the initial stages, what concerns them most is their survival from the brutal killings, murders and violent acts. However, after

the conflict continues for several months, they find survival difficult in relief camps due to lack of means of livelihood and many other problems faced day by day. Now, their primary concern is the means of livelihood, how to settle a family life again, and how to find a home. The state and central Government took the initiative. It took up some temporary solutions to their demand, like giving them shelter in relief camps, making specific relief camps in various parts of the state, and providing them with immediate small-scale industrial training in soap making, dish-washing, etc. However, this does not provide them complete security to livelihood and a permanent solution. Their problems and suffering are too huge as they cannot afford to educate their children, fulfill their hunger, or provide necessary necessities. Girls and women faced many other personal issues regarding health hygiene, such as lack of sanitary pads, pregnant women unable to have proper medicine facilities, child delivery cases during their stay in relief camps, lactating mothers among internally displaced persons were there and many others who have high blood pressure, cardiac problems were at high risk. There were specific reports of death within the relief camps. The shelters provided in relief camps are in clusters and lack privacy, unequal distribution of food, and lack of many essential commodities such as drinking water, toilets, food, and clothes as time passes. In the earlier days, relief camps had lots of donations and helped individuals and organizations besides the Government. However, the never-ending conflicts worsen the people's state as time passes. They started to take skill training, but the lack of a proper market forced them to sell their products on the road, making the passersby compelled to buy. Sometimes, even people passing by cannot afford to buy it every day and refuse to buy it. They have no proper place to sell their products and no money to fulfill their daily necessities.

The consequences of the people becoming worse daily as they have to continue the fight may not be the actual gunfight but the fight for survival. So, the Government's incapability and delayed actions of controlling the issue, as said by many organizations and people, do nothing but more harm to the people. The Government's immediate action may be a temporary solution. However, it is also necessary for the Government to think of a permanent solution for internally displaced persons and people of the state. The severity of vulnerability differs from that of internally displaced persons. Here, we cannot say that only the people involved in such conflict suffer; almost everyone in Manipur suffers, and every community suffers. There has been quite a misunderstanding between different communities residing in the state. A Conflict does not affect a particular group of people or a particular community. Human Society has different communities, races, features, languages, and cultures. However, the goal is to create a harmonious relationship, peaceful cooperation, and mutual understanding, and this is possible only when one considers humanity as its identity. Thus, as a solution to all this, a new form of governance is necessary to minimize

the problems of every community and the vulnerability of internally displaced persons. Thus, as a solution, new governance is likely to be the upcoming governance the state needs, i.e., meta-governance.

Actions Taken Up by Government and CSOS

Many political leaders like the union home minister and other prominent political leaders like Rahul Gandhi have visited Manipur to look over the state's ground situation and visit the victims of the ongoing conflict. Not only this, many militaries and paramilitary forces have also been deployed in the state to control the mob and any form of violence happening in the state, as well as brutal killings, cross-firing, and burning houses in the state of Manipur. Manipur has witnessed a civil war-like situation, as DR. Bimol Akoijam said in his interview. The conditions of the state are very critical. Law and order have failed to control the situation for more than a year despite political leaders' visits from the center and state. They have often tried to have a peace talk to negotiate, which they are still unable to do. Many CSOs have tried to come up with solutions, but all the efforts are in vain.

The people of Manipur are suffering to a certain extent, and many necessary immediate aids are provided to the victims, even at the individual level. The relief material supplies are provided mainly by individuals, local clubs, organizations, CSOs, and many others besides the Government. However, we can see a significant failure, undecided, and ineffective strategy, after all from the Government or governance. The ruling party and other political parties have discussed the issue even in Lok Sabha and the Lower House, but signs of peace or hope for the end of the conflict still need to be guaranteed or seen. The conflict has worsened the ties more and more among the different communities in the state. The prolonged conflict affects both the communities and other communities. So, it has become necessary for the intellectuals, leaders, and other prominent society-molding institutions to come up with a solution that can minimize the risk of vulnerability of the people as it has a significant impact on other political, social, and economic status of the society as well as the future of the society. The conflict has dramatically affected the all-round development of the state, too.

What Is Meta Governance?

Meta governance is defined as a practice by public authorities that entails the coordination of one or more governance modes by using different instruments, methods, and strategies to overcome governance failures. Meta governance, therefore, goes beyond the unproductive dichotomy in the 'from Government to

governance' debate. The concept of meta-governance has recently attracted considerable attention in the governance literature. In general, meta-governance solves governance failures (Jessop, 2011, 113; Lund 2009, 245, 246; Torfing & Triantafyllou, 2011, p. 2). It is, for example, regarded as an essential activity for enhancing accountability and transparency in governance networks, limiting the fragmentation of global sustainability governance, or successful governance of natural resource regions, amongst other things (Glasberg, 2011; Morrison 2016; Sørensen and Torfing 2009). Meta governance is often referred to in very general terms, such as the governance of governance or the organization of self-organization (Jessop, 1998; Kooiman & Jentoft, 2009; Sørensen & Torfing, 2009).

Conceptually, meta-governance appeared for the first time in the public administration and political science literature in the mid-1990s. Jessop (1997) and Kooiman (1993) were among the first to use the concept. However, their accounts of what constitutes meta-governance differ substantially. Jessop, a prominent scholar in critical state theory, considers meta-governance as the state's involvement in strategically organizing the context and ground rules for governance. Kooiman, whose work has been influential in the governance literature, describes meta-governance as the process in which the discussion, formulation, and application of values, norms, and principles for governance take place (Jessop, 1997; Kooiman & Jentoft, 2009).

Meta Governance as A Likely Solution for The Crisis

Considering the state's poor performance in law and order, failure to resolve the conflict, and lack of a safe home for internally displaced persons, meta-governance is the likely solution. Meta governance is often perceived as a solution to governance failures. As many scholars have researched and considered meta-governance adequate, it becomes clear that the meta-governor is often not a neutral broker in the governing process but rather an individual or organization that tries to further its policy goals. Also, meta-governance is used to increase the democratic legitimacy of governance networks. Besides intentional reasons such as the goal of more coordination or better democratic practices, some studies identified contextual reasons for meta-governance. Examples include changes in political-administrative systems, (geo) political conflicts, and external requirements by superior institutions or the law. Many scholars believe that meta-governance synthesizes the classical form of the 'Government to governance' debate. It is a valuable concept because it enables us to analyze the relationship between public authorities and governance networks. The concept of meta-governance is used loosely and with little operationalization in case studies in the literature. However,

its coordination, as the reason, for example, to decrease fragmentation, create coherency, aim for procedural harmony, or reduce overlap, might be handy in such multiple factors as ethnic conflicts.

Conclusion

The condition of the state is now very critical, and it would be unwise to say anything that can mislead the conflicts without proper research on the issue and have a peace talk as many would like to. The consequences of war will go backward in the development and growth of society. The number of people suffering will increase, and more unwanted crimes and killings may happen out of anger, aggressiveness, and necessity, which cannot be considered an immediate result of the conflict. However, indirectly, the consequences arise from the conflicts flaming in the state for over a year. The vulnerability of the IDPs becomes severe day by day, and it may become a massive flame of frustration, anxiety, and revenge, which will add fuel to the ongoing conflict. The causes of ongoing conflict have multiple sources, historically, politically, socially, and economically. Thus, the solution cannot be narrowed down and streamlined in one aspect. Thus, meta-governance is a likely solution since it is a network-based crisis. Thus, a safe and effective solution is necessary as soon as possible to stop such flames, which can be more severe than the ongoing conflict.

References

1. Voice of the People ep 07/12 June 26, 2023
2. Elite news June 27, 2023
3. Mojo story, Manipur Ground zero
4. Sm Vlog Naga
5. CNN News 8;kuki militants set ablaze houses@dolaithabi
6. The Tribune, Manipur; Kuki militants ambush a convoy of Bishnupur Police Commando(May 12, 2023)
7. Fresh gunfight@ Tera khongsangbi elte tv, 30th july
8. Elite TV 6:00 p. Eng news July 31 '23
9. Breaking News: Kuki lalhoubana attack tourakpada nupimacha ama sokle
10. June 28, Elite TV eng News 3 pm
11. UKLF claims to help the BJP in forming Govt. in Manipur (June 2014)

12. June 28; Elite tv 3pm Manipuri news eng news
13. 3rd June 2 pm Manipuri news
14. 29th june; elite tv 12;30 eng news
15. Suspected three Kuki militants had been killed and three others injured in the gun battle; July 8, 2023
16. Elite TV 12:30 pm eng news May 22, 2023
17. Elite TV, 2 00 pm Mani news 20th June SC rejects hearing on Kuki tribe & Manipur issue
18. Operation Yening; elite tv 6;00 pm eng news 8th july'2023
19. June 3rd , 2023: Yum mei thabda yaokhiba meina chakhibagi khudam ama fangle, elite tv
20. Fierce gunbattle at Gwaltabi in IE June 2023
21. Elite TV 8:30; Mani News 24th july:22 AR occupied previous bunker of meitei community@ Nongpok Ningthou, video footage providing food to them by Kuki women goes viral
22. Elite tv 8 30 pm Manipuri news June 3: Kuki militants torched sawmill and poultry farming @ Phayeng
23. Elite TV, 5 pm mani news June 5 '2023
24. Elite tv, 8:30 pm May 29
25. Elite news 7th and 8th july
26. Manipur violence| Escaping the conflict, Kuki families Find Haven in Delhi| The Quint, May 31, 2023.
27. Meta-governance: The Changing Role of Politicians in the process of Democratic Governance, Eva Sorensen, American Review of Public Administration, Volume 36 Number 1 March 2006 (98-114)
28. From Government to governance... to meta governance: a systematic literature review, Jonna Gjaltema, Robbert Biesbroek & Katein Termeer, Public Management Review, 22;12, 1760-1780

Publisher's Note: *The views and opinions expressed in this article are solely those of the author(s) and do not necessarily reflect those of the publisher, editors, or the editorial board.*